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Industrial Research Limited Report No. 961

The Welch-Satterthwaite formula and alternatives for the combination of uncertainties

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August 1999

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Industrial Research Limited Report 961

Reference

R. Willink; August 1999. The Welch-Satterthwaite formula and alternatives for the combination of uncertainties. Industrial Research Limited Report 961; Lower Hutt, New Zealand.

Summary and conclusions

The Welch-Satterthwaite formula is a simple commonly-used method for estimating the effective degrees of freedom associated with the combined uncertainty of a function of several input variables. This combined uncertainty and the effective degrees of freedom permit the calculation of a confidence interval for the quantity estimated by the function output under standard distributional assumptions.

Theoretical considerations suggested that the interval derived using the Welch-Satterthwaite formula might be improved upon, so various alternative formulae were developed. The main alternatives were developed for reduction of bias in the estimate of effective degrees of freedom, and for closer matching of the tails of the statistical t -distribution from which the confidence interval is calculated. The performances of the various confidence intervals were compared in simple cases involving 2 or 3 input variables.

The alternative formulae led to higher values of effective degrees of freedom than the Welch-Satterthwaite formula. Consequently the average widths of the alternative confidence intervals were lower, and generally the actual coverage probabilities of the confidence intervals were lower. Such an alternative could be regarded as superior to the Welch-Satterthwaite formula if used in instances where the alternative's coverage probability was higher than the stated level of, say, 95%.

The likely occurrence of such an instance can be suggested from the data. Therefore an improvement over a large range of possible input parameters seems possible by using a hybrid effective degrees of freedom, where the Welch-Satterthwaite formula is used in some cases and a bias-adjusted formula is used in other cases which are identified from the input data. However it is questionable whether the resulting reduction in the average width of the confidence intervals of less than 1% justifies the increased complexity of the method.

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1 Introduction

A quantity unable to be measured directly might be estimated by combining estimates of other, measurable, quantities according to the known functional relationship between them. For example, the volume of a cuboid might be estimated by multiplying estimates of its length, breadth and depth. Each individual estimate has an associated uncertainty, and each of these uncertainties may itself be imperfectly known, being based on a limited number of observations. An overall assessment of uncertainty requires the individual uncertainties to be combined into a single figure, and the numbers of observations to be combined into an *effective* number of total observations. Taylor series methods permit the uncertainty in the final quantity, e.g., the volume above, to be approximately expressed as the uncertainty in the sum of independent quantities, as in equation 10 in Section 5 of the 'Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement'[1]. This is the situation assumed in this report.

The so-called Welch-Satterthwaite formula of Annex G of [1] is one appropriate means of combining the uncertainties in these added quantities. The analysis is carried out not on the numbers of observations directly but on the closely related indices called the 'degrees of freedom'. More specifically, if the uncertainties in the estimates of m quantities are $u_1 \dots u_m$, with associated degrees of freedom $\nu_1 \dots \nu_m$, then the uncertainty in the estimate of the sum of the m quantities is

$$u_c = \sqrt{\sum u_i^2}, \quad (1)$$

where summation without limits denotes summation over $i = 1 \dots m$, and the associated effective number of degrees of freedom is

$$\nu_{ws} = \frac{(\sum u_i^2)^2}{\sum u_i^4 / \nu_i}. \quad (2)$$

The quantity u_c is the quantity $u_c(y)$ introduced in Section 5 of [1] while ν_{ws} is the effective degrees of freedom of Annex G of [1] denoted there by ν_{eff} . The subscript 'ws' is used here to indicate that this is the Welch-Satterthwaite formula.

These formulae are introduced here in the context of uncertainties obtained by random sampling, i.e. so-called Type A uncertainties[1]. However these formulae are also used with uncertainties based on prior knowledge, i.e. so-called Type B uncertainties, with individual input degrees of freedom defined using equation G.3 in Annex G of [1]. They are also used with combinations of Type A and Type B uncertainties.

The quantities u_c and ν_{ws} are not ends in themselves but are intermediate results used to find the width of an interval containing the unknown sum with a predefined level of confidence. Specifically, if \bar{x}_i is the estimate of the i 'th quantity then an approximate $(1 - \alpha) \times 100\%$ confidence interval for the sum is

$$\left[\sum \bar{x}_i - u_c t_{1-\alpha/2, \nu_{ws}}, \sum \bar{x}_i + u_c t_{1-\alpha/2, \nu_{ws}} \right]$$

where $t_{1-\alpha/2, \nu}$ is the $1 - \alpha/2$ quantile of Student's t -distribution with ν degrees of freedom. (For example $t_{0.975, 8} = 2.306$.) For simplicity this is written using a looser notation as

$$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_c t_{1-\alpha/2, \nu_{ws}}. \quad (3)$$

In this report we give a derivation of equation (2), and point to some weaknesses associated with it. Alternative equations are derived to address these weaknesses, and the merits of the various equations are assessed by comparing the performances of the resulting confidence intervals with that of (3).

2 Statistical background

The analysis leading to (3) is based on the assumption that each individual measurement of the i 'th quantity is independently drawn from a normal distribution centred on its true value. So the confidence interval gives an estimate of the sum of m normal means, where the m variances are unknown and unequal. To enable a fuller discussion of this we first describe a confidence interval for a single mean μ_i where i is fixed.

Suppose that $\{x_{i1} \dots x_{in_i}\}$ is a set of n_i independent measurements of the quantity μ_i . These measurements are assumed to be independently drawn from a normal distribution with unknown mean μ_i and an unknown variance denoted by σ_i^2 . All the information in the sample about μ_i and σ_i^2 is contained in the number of observations n_i , the sample mean

$$\bar{x}_i \equiv \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} x_{ij},$$

and the sample variance

$$s_i^2 \equiv \frac{1}{n_i-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_i)^2.$$

Therefore the optimal confidence interval for μ_i can be obtained from these quantities alone. By optimal we mean the shortest confidence interval with the specified confidence level. The shortest two-sided $(1 - \alpha) \times 100\%$ confidence interval for μ_i is the interval

$$\bar{x}_i \pm t_{1-\alpha/2, v_i} s_i / \sqrt{n_i} \quad (4)$$

where $v_i = n_i - 1$. Often we use $\alpha = 0.05$ to provide a 95% confidence interval, giving $1 - \alpha/2 = 0.975$. A common alternative is $\alpha = 0.01$. To relate this to the concept of uncertainty note that u_i , the uncertainty in \bar{x}_i as an estimate of μ_i , is given by

$$u_i \equiv s_i / \sqrt{n_i}$$

so the confidence interval for μ_i is $\bar{x}_i \pm u_i t_{1-\alpha/2, v_i}$.

The confidence interval (4) arises in the following way. Let Z be a standard normal random variable, i.e., a normal variable with mean 0 and variance 1, and let χ_v^2 be a random variable with the chi-squared distribution with v degrees of freedom. Then the ratio

$$Z \div \sqrt{\chi_v^2 / v} \quad (5)$$

has the t -distribution with v degrees of freedom. Now the quantity $(\bar{x}_i - \mu_i) \div (\sigma_i / \sqrt{n_i})$ has the standard normal distribution, and $v_i s_i^2 / \sigma_i^2$ independently has the chi-square distribution with v_i degrees of freedom. Therefore the ratio $(\bar{x}_i - \mu_i) \div (s_i / \sqrt{n_i})$ has the t -distribution with v_i degrees of freedom. This manipulation has obtained an expression in which the unknown parameter σ_i^2 , which is a nuisance parameter in making inference about μ_i , does not feature. Values of μ_i making the modulus of this ratio too large to have occurred by chance are excluded from the confidence interval

3 History

The problem above is a generalisation of the case where $m = 2$. This special case is itself equivalent to the problem of finding a confidence interval for the difference of two normal means, because the second variable can be arbitrarily negated. In turn this is statistically equivalent to testing the difference of means of two normal distributions with unknown and unequal variances, σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 , a problem known as the Behrens-Fisher problem. In connection with the case of $m = 2$ Welch[2] proposed that the distribution from which

$$s_1^2/n_1 + s_2^2/n_2$$

is drawn can be approximated by that of $b\chi_v^2$ where

$$b = \frac{\sigma_1^4/n_1^2\nu_1 + \sigma_2^4/n_2^2\nu_2}{\sigma_1^2/n_1 + \sigma_2^2/n_2} \quad (7)$$

and

$$v = \frac{(\sigma_1^2/n_1 + \sigma_2^2/n_2)^2}{\sigma_1^4/n_1^2\nu_1 + \sigma_2^4/n_2^2\nu_2}, \quad (8)$$

These values of the parameters are such that the means and variances of the two distributions are matched. Provided the unknown variances σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 are replaced by their sample estimates s_1^2 and s_2^2 these equations can then be used to assess the equality of means μ_1 and μ_2 . The resulting formula for the degrees of freedom is equivalent to (2) with $m = 2$. Satterthwaite[3] considered the case of more general m and obtained in essence equation 2. An earlier result for $m = 2$ was published by Smith[4].

An exact but difficult series solution to the problem for general m was subsequently put forward by Welch[5], and associated tables for the case of $m = 2$ were provided by Aspin[6]. Also, for an approximation involving the chi-squared distribution with an effective degrees of freedom Welch[5] suggested the use of equation (14) below. For any future developments this later paper by Welch appears to be the most important of those referenced here.

4 Derivation of the Welch-Satterthwaite formula

In this section we give a derivation and justification of equations (1) and (2). The problem at hand is to approximate the distribution of $\sum u_i^2 = \sum s_i^2/n_i$ by the distribution of a scaled chi-square variable, $b\chi_v^2$. The normal theory of section 2 implies that $\sum u_i^2$ is a linear combination of chi-squared random variables, $\sum u_i^2 = \sum a_i\chi_{\nu_i}^2$, where

$$a_i \equiv \sigma_i^2/n_i\nu_i.$$

A solution technique giving (2) is the method of moments, which is a standard technique for approximating a difficult probability distribution by a simpler one. Here the distribution of $\sum u_i^2$ is approximated is that of a linear combination of chi-squared random $\sum u_i^2 = \sum a_i\chi_{\nu_i}^2$, where

$$a_i \equiv \sigma_i^2/n_i\nu_i,$$

as seen from the normal theory of section 2. Suppose the approximating distribution is defined by n parameters. The method of moments, as usually applied, finds the values of these parameters by equating the lowest n moments of the two distributions. Using the lowest n moments means the results are unaffected by taking different moments about different origins. Therefore the method of moments chooses the parameters b and v so that the associated mean and variance match those of the linear combination. The equations matching these quantities are

$$\begin{aligned}bv &= \sum a_i v_i \\ 2b^2 v &= 2 \sum a_i^2 v_i\end{aligned}$$

with solutions

$$\begin{aligned}b &= \frac{\sum a_i^2 v_i}{\sum a_i v_i} \\ v &= \frac{(\sum a_i v_i)^2}{\sum a_i^2 v_i}.\end{aligned}$$

Substituting for the a_i values gives

$$b_{12} = \frac{\sum \sigma_i^4 / n_i^2 v_i}{\sum \sigma_i^2 / n_i} \quad (9)$$

$$v_{12} = \frac{(\sum \sigma_i^2 / n_i)^2}{\sum \sigma_i^4 / n_i^2 v_i} \quad (10)$$

where the subscript '12' is introduced to denote the theoretical solution using the first and second moments. These equations are generalisations of (7) and (8) for all m . To estimate these quantities the true variances $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ can be replaced by their estimates $\{s_i^2\}$ to obtain (1) and (2) because $u_i^2 = s_i^2 / n_i$.

5 Applicability

It is well known that the sum of chi-squared random variables $\sum \chi_{v_i}^2$ is distributed exactly as χ_λ^2 where $\lambda = \sum v_i$. Therefore, if each a_i coefficient is equal the distribution corresponding to b_{12} and v_{12} found by the method of moments is exact, and performance is expected to deteriorate as the a_i values diverge. In particular the worst case appears to be when low values of a_i are associated with high values of v_i . This occurs when the values of σ_i^2 / n_i are comparable but the values of v_i are widespread. The squared uncertainties u_i^2 might then be comparable but the degrees of freedom are not. Those uncertainties with high values of v_i are better estimates of the underlying σ_i^2 / n_i values.

The opposite case where a particularly high value of a_i is associated with a high value of v_i would not seem to present a problem. In the extreme case this uncertainty dominates and the linear combination is approximated well by the distribution of $a_i \chi_{v_i}^2$.

The suggestion is that equations (1)-(3) will perform best when the $a_i = \sigma_i^2 / n_i (n_i - 1)$ values are similar, notwithstanding the effect of using s_i^2 for σ_i^2 .

Suppose the orders of magnitude of the m variances σ_i^2 were known, and for reasons of practicality or economy the total number of observations $\sum n_i$ was fixed. Then

distributing this number of observations among the m variables so that the resulting unknowns a_i were each of a similar size would lead to a more accurate confidence interval. However this wouldn't be the narrowest interval, which would be obtained when the $u_i^2 = \sigma_i^2/n_i$ values were comparable.

We shall see in section 9 that (1) and the Welch-Satterthwaite formula (2) performs surprisingly well so the comments in this section might be regarded as unimportant.

6 Alternatives for reduced bias

In this section alternatives to v_{ws} are described which are designed to be less biased as estimators of the theoretical solution v_{12} . In as much as v_{12} is the best figure for an effective degrees of freedom these alternatives might be expected to give more accurate confidence intervals than v_{ws} .

The estimates $\{s_i^2\}$ are unbiased estimates of the unknown variances $\{\sigma_i^2\}$. By definition this means that

$$E[s_i^2] = \sigma_i^2 \quad i = 1 \dots m$$

where $E[\cdot]$ denotes the expectation. However s_i^4 is not an unbiased estimate of σ_i^4 so the numerator and denominator in (2) are not unbiased estimates of the numerator and denominator in (10). Even if they were, the quotient (2) would not in general be an unbiased estimate of (10). Therefore replacing the unknown variances $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ by the sample variances $\{s_i^2\}$ leads to an estimate of the effective degrees of freedom v_{ws} which is biased with respect to the method-of-moments solution v_{12} . An attempt to correct for the bias might be expected to give confidence intervals with improved performance.

An estimate of the bias in (2) can be found using a technique known as the method of statistical differentials (or delta method), in which the expected value of a function of random variables can be approximated by expanding the function as a Taylor series about the expected values of its random variables. Let $f(\cdot)$ be the function of random variables $\{V_i\}$ with expected values $\{\zeta_i\}$. The expected value of the function is

$$E[f(\{V_i\})] \approx f(\{\zeta_i\}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \text{var}(V_i) \frac{\partial^2 f(\{\zeta_j\})}{\partial \zeta_i^2} + \dots$$

[7, pp.646-7] where the second order terms not shown are proportional to the covariances between different random variables, and the other terms not shown are of higher order. Let V_i be the random variable for u_i^2 so $\zeta_i = \sigma_i^2/n_i$, and let $f(\cdot)$ have the form of the right-hand side of (2). Then the covariance terms mentioned above are all zero and, after considerable analysis, the expected value of (the random variable for) v_{ws} including all second order terms is

$$E[v_{ws}] \approx v_{12} + 2 - 2v_{12}^2 \frac{\sum (\sigma_i^2/n_i v_i)^2}{(\sum \sigma_i^2/n_i)^2} - 8v_{12}^2 \frac{\sum \sigma_i^6/n_i^3 v_i^2}{(\sum \sigma_i^2/n_i)^3} + 8v_{12}^3 \frac{\sum \sigma_i^8/n_i^4 v_i^3}{(\sum \sigma_i^2/n_i)^4}. \quad (11)$$

(For simplicity the notation v_{ws} here denotes a random variable and not its observed value.) So the bias in v_{ws} as an estimate of v_{12} caused by substituting s_i^2 for σ_i^2 is approximately equal to the last four terms shown. To correct for the bias these last terms are themselves approximated using the sample variances and then subtracted from the biased estimate v_{ws} . Using all of these terms gives one alternative number of

effective degrees of freedom, denoted by v_{ba}^* , say, but using only the first two terms gives a simpler alternative

$$v_{ba} = v_{ws} - 2 + 2v_{ws} \frac{\sum u_i^4/v_i^2}{\sum u_i^4/v_i} \quad (12)$$

which written explicitly is

$$v_{ba} = \frac{(\sum u_i^2)^2}{\sum u_i^4/v_i} - 2 + 2 \frac{(\sum u_i^2)^2 \sum u_i^4/v_i^2}{(\sum u_i^4/v_i)^2}. \quad (13)$$

The expanded denominator of the ratio in the third term in equation (13) contains the term u_i^8/v_i^2 for each i which is matched by a term in the numerator. The denominator also contains the term $2u_i^4 u_j^4/v_i v_j$ for each combination of i and j where $i > j$, but the numerator contains the term $u_i^4 u_j^4/v_i^2 + u_i^4 u_j^4/v_j^2$, which is not smaller. The denominator contains no other terms but, if $m > 1$, the numerator contains other terms which are all positive. It follows that, for $m > 1$, the ratio in the third term is greater than or equal to 1 so the bias adjustment increases the estimated effective degrees of freedom, i.e., $v_{ba} > v_{ws}$, which in the absence of other changes will produce a narrower confidence interval. So, provided the actual level of confidence does not drop below the nominal level $(1 - \alpha) \times 100\%$, the confidence intervals will be improved.

A third possibility is to consider the ratio of an unbiased estimator of the numerator of (10) to an unbiased estimator of the denominator of (10). This is

$$v_{ba, welch} = \frac{(\sum u_i^2)^2 - 2 \sum u_i^4/(v_i + 2)}{\sum u_i^4/(v_i + 2)} = \frac{(\sum u_i^2)^2}{\sum u_i^4/(v_i + 2)} - 2. \quad (14)$$

which is a choice put forward in the later paper by Welch[5]. The exact solution presented in that paper gives further insight into the nature of the approximation (14) and gives support to its use.

The performances of v_{ba}^* , v_{ba} and $v_{ba, welch}$ are discussed in section 9.

7 Modification for matching the lower tail

This section presents alternatives to v_{ws} obtained by improving the chi-square approximation at the lower tail of the distribution; this being the tail with greater influence on the performance of the resulting confidence interval.

The method of moments as applied in the previous sections provides an approximation to the whole distribution of $\sum a_i \chi_i^2$. However, because the χ^2 distribution appears in the denominator of the ratio (5), large values of $|t|$ are associated primarily with small values of χ^2 . Therefore the calculated confidence interval (3) might be improved upon if the approximating scaled chi-squared distribution were chosen to provide a better match at the lower tail at the expense of the upper tail. This can be achieved by matching a 'higher' pair of moments about an origin at the upper end of the distribution [8], because the lower tail of the distribution contributes proportionately more to such moments.

Consider matching the first and third moments about a point r . Let X be a random variable with mean μ^* . Then, writing $(X - r) = (X - \mu^*) + (\mu^* - r)$ shows the third moment about r to be

$$E(X - r)^3 = E(X - \mu^*)^3 + 3(\mu^* - r)E(X - \mu^*)^2 + (\mu^* - r)^3.$$

The first expectation on the right-hand side, being the third central moment, is also the third cumulant. The second expectation is the variance, which is the second cumulant, and the mean is the first cumulant. Cumulants add linearly under linear combination of variables, so if μ , μ_2 and μ_3 are the mean, variance and third central moment of the linear combination $\sum a_i \chi_i^2$ then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu &= \sum \sigma_i^2/n_i \\ \mu_2 &= 2 \sum \sigma_i^4/n_i^2 v_i \\ \mu_3 &= 8 \sum \sigma_i^6/n_i^3 v_i^2,\end{aligned}$$

and the equations matching the first and third moments about r of this distribution to those of the approximating distribution $b\chi_v^2$ are

$$\begin{aligned}\mu - r &= bv - r \\ \mu_3 + 3(\mu - r)\mu_2 + (\mu - r)^3 &= 8b^3v + 6(bv - r)b^2v + (bv - r)^3.\end{aligned}$$

The first equation allows μ to be substituted for bv in the right-hand side of the second equation to give the quadratic equation

$$8\mu b^2 + 6\mu(\mu - r)b - [\mu_3 + 3(\mu - r)\mu_2] = 0,$$

which can be solved to find a positive value of b . The origin r is to lie in the upper portion of the distribution, so it is convenient to work instead with moderate values of

$$k \equiv (r - \mu)/\sqrt{\mu_2}.$$

Thus k is the number of standard deviations that r lies above the mean of the distribution to be approximated. Suitable values of k will be moderate so that quantiles in the upper tail are close to r so that the corresponding probability elements carry little weight in the moment calculations compared to those in the lower tail. (Values of k considered in the simulations of section 9 are $\sqrt{0.5}$, 1 and $\sqrt{2}$.) The positive solution to the quadratic equation is

$$b_{13} = \frac{3k\sqrt{\mu_2}}{8} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{8\mu_3}{9k^2\mu_2\mu} - \frac{8\sqrt{\mu_2}}{3k\mu}} \right),$$

where the subscript '13' indicates the matching of first and third moments. The corresponding effective degrees of freedom is $v_{13} = \mu/b_{13}$ which, because $\mu^2/\mu_2 = v_{12}/2$, can be written as

$$v_{13} = \frac{8\sqrt{v_{12}}}{3k\sqrt{2}} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{32v_{12}\sum \sigma_i^6/n_i^3 v_i^2}{9k^2(\sum \sigma_i^2/n_i)^3} - \frac{8\sqrt{2}}{3k\sqrt{v_{12}}}} \right)^{-1}.$$

To estimate v_{13} the unknown variances, σ_i^2 , can be replaced by the sample variances, s_i^2 , so σ_i^2/n_i is replaced by u_i^2 . The resulting estimate is

$$v_{1t} = \frac{8\sqrt{v_{ws}}}{3k\sqrt{2}} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{32v_{ws}\sum u_i^6/v_i^2}{9k^2(\sum u_i^2)^3} - \frac{8\sqrt{2}}{3k\sqrt{v_{ws}}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where the subscript '1t' denotes the matching by the lower tail.

Approximate bias adjustment might be made to this equation by using unbiased or less-biased estimates of contributing quantities. Therefore v_{bi} might be used instead of

v_{ws} to estimate v_{12} and an unbiased estimate of $\sigma_i^6/n_i^3v^2$ used instead of u_i^6/v^2 . For an normal population an unbiased estimate of σ_i^6 is $s_i^6/(1 + 6/v_i + 8/v_i^2)$ meaning an unbiased estimate of $\sigma_i^6/n_i^3v_i^2$ is $u_i^6/(v_i^2 + 6v_i + 8)$. So an alternative to v_{lt} with some bias adjustment is

$$v_{ltba} = \frac{8\sqrt{v_{ba}}}{3k\sqrt{2}} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{32v_{ba} \sum u_i^6 / (v_i^2 + 6v_i + 8)}{9k^2 (\sum u_i^2)^3} - \frac{8\sqrt{2}}{3k\sqrt{v_{ba}}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (16)$$

The performances of v_{lt} and v_{ltba} are discussed in section 9.

It is worth noting one reason why these estimates of effective degrees of freedom might not be as suitable as, for example, v_{ws} or v_{ba} as degrees of freedom for input to *subsequent* calculations. While large values of $|t|$ are associated primarily with small values of χ^2 in the single case, they are not necessarily associated primarily with small values of every component χ^2 in subsequent cases. The principle of down-weighting the upper tail might then lead to unwanted errors. Thus v_{lt} and v_{ltba} are perhaps less transferable estimates than v_{ws} or v_{ba} .

8 A Bayesian solution

In this section we describe a method compatible with the Bayesian philosophy of probability. This is achieved by first referring to the concept of 'fiducial' probability which is little-known and out of favour.

The methods described so far are derived using classical statistical theory where the parameters $\{\mu_i\}$ are regarded as being fixed. So to this point we have regarded \bar{x}_i as being distributed around μ_i and not vice versa. However, because

$$\frac{\bar{x}_i - \mu_i}{u_i}$$

is drawn from the t -distribution with v_i degrees of freedom, it might be suggested that μ_i is in some sense distributed around \bar{x}_i with the same t -distribution scaled by u_i . A probability distribution in this sense is called a fiducial distribution. The concept of fiducial probability is associated with Fisher (e.g. [9]). Thus μ_i is distributed (fiducially) as $\bar{x}_i + u_i t_{v_i}$. Consequently $\sum \mu_i$ is distributed (fiducially) as the linear combination of t -variables, $\sum u_i t_{v_i}$. This distribution can be approximated by a single scaled t -distribution, $u_{\bar{n}} t_{v_{\bar{n}}}$ by applying the method of moments, where the second and fourth moments are matched because the odd moments of t -distributions are zero. If we denote the variance of $u_i t_{v_i}$ by

$$g_i \equiv u_i^2 v_i / (v_i - 2)$$

then matching the variances means satisfying the equation

$$\sum g_i = \frac{u_{\bar{n}}^2 v_{\bar{n}}}{v_{\bar{n}} - 2},$$

while matching the fourth central moments simultaneously with the variances is equivalent to matching the fourth cumulants by satisfying

$$\sum \frac{6g_i^2}{v_i - 4} = \left(\frac{u_{\bar{n}}^2 v_{\bar{n}}}{v_{\bar{n}} - 2} \right)^2 \frac{6}{v_{\bar{n}} - 4}.$$

The solutions are

$$v_{fi} = \frac{(\sum g_i)^2}{\sum g_i^2 / (v_i - 4)} + 4 \quad (17)$$

$$u_{fi} = \sqrt{\frac{(v_{fi} - 2)}{v_{fi}} \sum g_i} \quad (18)$$

where these can be seen to be extensions of the solutions for $m = 2$ given by Patil[11]. Note that v_{fi} can not be calculated if $v_i < 4$ for any i , and may sensibly be defined to be 4 if $v_i = 4$ for any i .

In Bayesian statistics belief about a parameter before observation of data is expressed in terms of a prior probability distribution for the parameter. This prior distribution is modified using the information provided by the data to obtain a posterior distribution for the parameter. Broadly speaking, the behaviour of the posterior distribution is dominated by the data if the amount of data is large, but is dominated by the prior distribution if the amount of data is small. For many classical statisticians, the step of subjectively choosing the initial prior distribution is unacceptable.

The same distribution $\bar{x}_i + u_{it}v_i$ for v_i can be found by a Bayesian analysis assuming a uniform prior distribution for μ_i and the prior density of $f_{\sigma_i^2}(x) \propto 1/x$ for σ_i^2 , [10, pp.68-71]. Therefore (17) and (18) not only represent solutions following the fiducial concept of probability, which is currently not much used, but also possible Bayesian solutions. The prior densities chosen are non-informative in that they are chosen to represent prior ignorance about the mean μ_i and the logarithm of the variance.

Alternative "conjugate" choices of prior distribution for μ_i and σ_i^2 exist which lead to a similar simple expression for the posterior distribution of μ_i [10, pp.73-76].

9 Evaluation of the alternatives

The usefulness of each estimate of effective degrees of freedom is largely determined by the performance of its associated confidence interval. In this section the performances of the various confidence intervals are compared, where these intervals are given the classical interpretation. The intervals studied included

$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{ws}}$	for v_{ws} of (2)
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{ba}^*}$	for v_{ba}^* of section 6
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{ba}}$	for v_{ba} of (12)
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{ba, welch}}$	for $v_{ba, welch}$ of (14)
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{lt}}$	for $k = \sqrt{0.5}, 1, \sqrt{2}$ for v_{lt} of (15)
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{ct} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{ltba}}$	for various k for v_{ltba} of (16)
$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_{fi} t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{fi}}$	for v_{fi} of (17)

The user is interested in the width of a confidence interval and the quoted confidence level, which may differ from the actual level of confidence. The actual level of confidence is the actual probability that the interval will contain the true parameter when the interval is (correctly) viewed as a function of unobserved random data. Ideally the width is small, the quoted confidence level is high and the actual level of confidence is equal to, or exceeds, the quoted value. The quoted confidence level is

somewhat arbitrary, so the degrees to which the other two criteria are satisfied are taken as performance measures for the intervals. So in the simulations described below the intervals were compared according to their mean widths and actual levels of confidence, also called actual coverage probabilities, for nominal levels of 95% and 99%.

Another performance criterion which would be relevant to a user repeatedly calculating confidence intervals under similar conditions is the variability of the widths of the confidence intervals. Intervals with widths considerably more variable than those for v_{ws} might not be favoured. Briefs results for this are mentioned.

As described in section 2 the confidence interval is a random interval calculated to have a nominal probability of encompassing the parameter of interest before observation of the data. This suggests that a proper simulation comparison of the various intervals involves generating many random sets of uncertainties $\{u_i\}$ for various settings of the parameters. Different intervals may be superior for different settings of the parameters $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ and $\{n_i\}$, but because the parameters $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ are unobservable in practice this information is of limited value. Note that this differs from 'generating' many sets of the variances $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ for chosen settings of the observations $\{u_i^2\}$ and $\{n_i\}$. This latter approach would be appropriate if the intervals studied were interpreted as Bayesian confidence intervals, sometimes called 'credibility intervals'[12], rather than classical confidence intervals.

9.1 Method and results

A large number of replications were performed for each of several settings of the parameter sets $\{\sigma_i^2\}$ and $\{n_i\}$. In each case the parameters $\{\mu_i\}$ could be set to zero for simplicity. This loses no generality because the effect of varying the sum of means $\sum \mu_i$ is simply to translate the distribution of $\sum \bar{x}_i$ by the same amount. So the true sum of means in each simulation is zero, and the calculated confidence interval contains this true mean if half its width is equal to or greater than $\sum \bar{x}_i$.

For computational reasons simulations were carried out only with $m = 2$ and $m = 3$. For each setting of the parameters 1000 or 100,000 sets of $\{u_i\}$ values were generated. For each of these sets the various intervals were calculated. The summarising information for each proposed interval comprises the mean half-width of the interval and the proportion of occasions the interval contained the point zero, which nominally is $1 - \alpha$.

Results are given in Tables 1-3, and Figures 1 and 2, where at all times it was possible to set $a_1 = 1$ without loss of generality because the common scale of the a_i values is of no relevance. For recorded coverage probabilities in the region of the nominal value, $p = 1 - \alpha/2$ the standard uncertainties in these individual figures from n simulations can be taken to be $\sqrt{p(1-p)/n}$ using binomial theory. However each interval was calculated from each individual set of simulated data. Therefore the proportions within each row are not independent. These standard uncertainties are given.

The preliminary results of Table 1 and other results (with 10,000 runs) showed that using v_{ws} provided an actual level of confidence surprisingly close to the nominal level of 0.95. In keeping with the relationship $v_{ba} > v_{ws}$, using v_{ba} lowered the average width of the interval, where the reduction was by between 0 and 5%, with 1% being a summary figure. However using v_{ba} also lowered the actual level of confidence in some cases to a value below 0.95, so that no superiority could be claimed. Results for $v_{ba, welch}$ were almost indistinguishable from those for v_{ba} . Using v_{ba}^* did not appear to

improve on v_{ws} . Using v_{lt} with $k = \sqrt{0.5}$ lowered the average widths by similar amounts, but gave actual levels of confidence which were more varied. Using higher values of k , namely 1 and $\sqrt{2}$ led to the effects being less marked. The estimate v_{ltba} was sometimes unable to be calculated when the degrees of freedom were few (presumably because of negative values beneath the square root sign) and so was unsatisfactory. Where calculable the intervals obtained using v_{fi} were broader on average than the intervals with v_{ws} and had a higher actual degree of confidence, and were only calculable because neither v_1 nor v_2 was very small.

It is perhaps unfair to evaluate Bayesian or Fiducial solutions e.g. v_{fi} , using this method because they are derived from alternative views of probability, and in effect are derived to answer a different question. Nevertheless the comparison stands if it is understood that they are being evaluated as if they were proposed confidence intervals for communication to a client who applied the classical interpretation.

So, if a potential reduction of 1% in the width of a confidence interval is enough to suggest using a more complicated estimate than v_{ws} , there seems to be merit in considering an equation designed to perform like v_{ba} when the unknown a_i values are equal and v_{ws} is sufficiently large, but like v_{ws} when they are considerably different or when v_{ws} is small. Therefore a hybrid approach is chosen. When the a_i values are equal we expect the values of u_i^2/v_i to be similar so that

$$r \equiv \frac{\sum u_i^4/v_i^2}{(\sum u_i^2/v_i)^2} \approx 1/m.$$

When the a_i values differ greatly $r \approx 1$. This suggests a degrees of freedom estimate such as

$$v_{hy} = \begin{cases} v_{ws} & \text{if } v_{ws} < 7 \text{ or } r > 0.25 \left(\frac{m-1}{m} \right) + \frac{1}{m} \\ v_{ba} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

(where the coefficient 0.25 is moderate), and using the interval

$$\sum \bar{x}_i \pm u_c t_{1-\alpha/2, v_{hy}}.$$

The results of a study of the intervals using v_{ws} , v_{ba} and v_{hy} with a larger number of simulations, 100,000, are given in Table 2, while results for $\alpha = 0.01$, i.e. 99% confidence levels, and 100,000 simulations are given in Table 3.

Summary results of Table 2 are presented in a more immediate way in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 compares the performance of v_{ba} with v_{ws} . The x-axis labels gives the ratio of the coefficients a_i/a_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$, following a natural ordering. The y-axis labels give the corresponding degrees of freedom v_i, v_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$, where each case is chosen to have $v_i \leq v_j$. The y-axis is ordered by $v_i + v_j$. The entry in the body of the figure is the proportional reduction in average width of the interval when moving from v_{ws} to v_{ba} expressed in tenths of percent. The widths used in these calculations were the verbatim widths of Table 2, i.e. widths rounded to 3 decimal places. Thus the maximum observed reduction in interval width was 5.4% observed with $a_1 = a_2$ and $v_1 = 3, v_2 = 3$. Entries are only given for the parameter settings where v_{ba} is deemed to perform equally well or better than v_{ws} (in terms of coverage). These settings are those for which the coverage of v_{ba} as recorded to 3 decimal places in Table 2 was equal to or exceeded 0.949 (to allow for the standard uncertainty of 0.0007), or was equal to the coverage of v_{ws} . Figure 2 compares the performance of v_{hy} with v_{ws} in the same way. It can be seen that using v_{hy} instead of v_{ba} reduces the improvement in performance present for some settings of the parameters but gives equal or better performance than v_{ws} for more general parameter settings. Reference to Table 2 will show that where entries are not given in Figure 2 the coverage probabilities of v_{hy} were close to those of v_{ws} .

Table 1 Performances of the 95% confidence intervals for $m = 2$ for 1000 runs at various settings of the parameters σ_1^2 , σ_2^2 , n_1 and n_2 where

$$V_i = n_i - 1 \quad a_i = \sigma_i^2/n_i V_i \quad i = 1, 2.$$

cov = actual coverage probability (standard uncertainty = 0.007) wid = average half-width of interval

d_1	d_2	V_1	V_2	V_{ws} cov	wid	V_{ba^*} cov	wid	V_{ba} cov	wid	$V_{h, k=\sqrt{0.5}}$ cov	wid	$V_{h, k=1}$ cov	wid	$V_{h, k=\sqrt{2}}$ cov	wid	V_h cov	wid	$V_{h, k=\sqrt{2}}$ cov	wid	$V_{h, k=\sqrt{2}}$ cov	wid	$V_{h, k=\sqrt{2}}$ cov	wid
1	1	5	5	0.951	0.700	0.947	0.696	0.946	0.685	0.946	0.678	0.950	0.692	0.950	0.696	0.968	0.791	0.946	0.685	0.946	0.685		
1	1	5	8	0.957	0.783	0.956	0.780	0.954	0.773	0.956	0.772	0.956	0.779	0.957	0.781	0.975	0.864	0.954	0.773	0.954	0.773		
1	1	5	12	0.950	0.869	0.950	0.866	0.950	0.863	0.950	0.863	0.950	0.866	0.950	0.867	0.960	0.940	0.950	0.862	0.950	0.862		
1	1	8	5	0.949	0.776	0.949	0.773	0.948	0.766	0.948	0.766	0.949	0.772	0.949	0.774	0.962	0.855	0.948	0.766	0.948	0.766		
1	1	8	8	0.953	0.835	0.953	0.832	0.950	0.828	0.950	0.830	0.953	0.833	0.953	0.834	0.965	0.897	0.950	0.828	0.950	0.828		
1	1	8	12	0.959	0.927	0.959	0.925	0.956	0.922	0.957	0.924	0.924	0.926	0.959	0.926	0.968	0.982	0.956	0.922	0.956	0.922		
1	1	12	5	0.948	0.855	0.947	0.852	0.947	0.848	0.947	0.850	0.948	0.853	0.948	0.854	0.966	0.926	0.947	0.848	0.947	0.848		
1	1	12	8	0.947	0.928	0.947	0.926	0.947	0.923	0.947	0.925	0.947	0.927	0.947	0.928	0.956	0.983	0.947	0.923	0.947	0.923		
1	1	12	12	0.950	1.006	0.949	1.004	0.946	1.002	0.947	1.004	0.948	1.005	0.949	1.006	0.956	1.053	0.946	1.002	0.946	1.002		
5	5	5	5	0.956	1.268	0.957	1.280	0.955	1.246	0.950	1.186	0.954	1.243	0.956	1.257	0.966	1.372	0.955	1.246	0.955	1.246		
5	5	8	5	0.934	1.448	0.935	1.450	0.933	1.438	0.932	1.424	0.933	1.439	0.933	1.443	0.943	1.516	0.933	1.438	0.933	1.438		
5	5	12	5	0.953	1.717	0.953	1.718	0.952	1.713	0.952	1.709	0.953	1.714	0.953	1.715	0.958	1.766	0.952	1.713	0.952	1.713		
5	5	8	8	0.949	1.289	0.951	1.308	0.946	1.265	0.944	1.217	0.947	1.261	0.949	1.275	0.968	1.400	0.946	1.265	0.946	1.265		
5	5	8	5	0.953	1.481	0.953	1.486	0.952	1.470	0.951	1.454	0.952	1.470	0.953	1.475	0.957	1.549	0.952	1.470	0.952	1.470		
5	5	8	12	0.947	1.735	0.947	1.737	0.947	1.730	0.947	1.725	0.947	1.730	0.947	1.732	0.953	1.781	0.947	1.730	0.947	1.730		
5	5	12	5	0.946	1.323	0.949	1.346	0.945	1.300	0.942	1.263	0.944	1.297	0.945	1.310	0.965	1.445	0.945	1.300	0.945	1.300		
5	5	12	8	0.948	1.557	0.949	1.566	0.948	1.546	0.946	1.528	0.948	1.545	0.948	1.550	0.960	1.631	0.948	1.546	0.948	1.546		
5	5	12	12	0.949	1.768	0.949	1.771	0.949	1.762	0.949	1.755	0.949	1.762	0.949	1.764	0.954	1.816	0.949	1.762	0.949	1.762		
1	20	5	5	0.942	2.438	0.942	2.460	0.938	2.416	0.920	2.225	0.934	2.394	0.938	2.421	0.945	2.513	0.938	2.416	0.938	2.416		
1	20	5	8	0.955	2.849	0.955	2.855	0.953	2.843	0.952	2.809	0.953	2.839	0.953	2.844	0.959	2.890	0.953	2.843	0.953	2.843		
1	20	5	12	0.948	3.334	0.949	3.336	0.948	3.332	0.948	3.325	0.948	3.331	0.948	3.332	0.950	3.362	0.948	3.332	0.948	3.332		
1	20	8	5	0.950	2.458	0.951	2.491	0.946	2.428	0.930	2.248	0.945	2.401	0.947	2.434	0.961	2.548	0.946	2.428	0.946	2.428		
1	20	8	8	0.952	2.857	0.952	2.867	0.951	2.847	0.949	2.806	0.951	2.842	0.951	2.850	0.957	2.905	0.951	2.847	0.951	2.847		
1	20	8	12	0.941	3.330	0.941	3.334	0.941	3.327	0.941	3.317	0.941	3.325	0.941	3.328	0.941	3.359	0.941	3.327	0.941	3.327		
1	20	12	5	0.948	2.439	0.952	2.486	0.943	2.402	0.930	2.242	0.940	2.373	0.945	2.410	0.959	2.555	0.943	2.402	0.943	2.402		
1	20	12	8	0.952	2.855	0.953	2.869	0.951	2.842	0.949	2.795	0.950	2.834	0.952	2.845	0.953	2.913	0.951	2.842	0.951	2.842		
1	20	12	12	0.948	3.373	0.948	3.378	0.948	3.368	0.947	3.355	0.948	3.366	0.948	3.369	0.948	3.407	0.948	3.368	0.948	3.368		
100	5	5	5	0.945	5.395	0.946	5.410	0.945	5.381	0.932	4.908	0.944	5.356	0.945	5.382	0.948	5.435	0.945	5.381	0.945	5.381		
100	5	8	5	0.949	6.346	0.950	6.350	0.948	6.342	0.946	6.308	0.947	6.339	0.948	6.343	0.953	6.366	0.948	6.342	0.948	6.342		
100	5	12	5	0.955	7.351	0.955	7.353	0.955	7.351	0.955	7.346	0.955	7.350	0.955	7.351	0.956	7.366	0.955	7.351	0.955	7.351		
100	8	5	5	0.943	5.376	0.946	5.399	0.942	5.354	0.929	4.888	0.940	5.319	0.942	5.357	0.947	5.429	0.942	5.354	0.942	5.354		
100	8	8	8	0.951	6.409	0.951	6.415	0.951	6.404	0.950	6.356	0.951	6.398	0.951	6.404	0.953	6.433	0.951	6.404	0.951	6.404		
100	8	12	8	0.955	7.407	0.955	7.408	0.955	7.405	0.955	7.398	0.955	7.403	0.955	7.405	0.955	7.420	0.955	7.405	0.955	7.405		
100	12	5	5	0.951	5.483	0.951	5.517	0.949	5.452	0.936	4.984	0.947	5.406	0.949	5.456	0.955	5.553	0.949	5.452	0.949	5.452		
100	12	8	8	0.925	6.270	0.927	6.279	0.925	6.262	0.922	6.201	0.924	6.254	0.925	6.263	0.928	6.300	0.925	6.262	0.925	6.262		
100	12	12	12	0.953	7.406	0.953	7.409	0.953	7.403	0.951	7.394	0.953	7.401	0.953	7.404	0.953	7.422	0.953	7.403	0.953	7.403		

Table 2

Performances of 95% confidence intervals for $m = 2$ for 100,000 runs at various settings of the parameters $\sigma_1^2, \sigma_2^2, n_1$ and n_2 where

$$v_i = n_i - 1 \quad a_i = \sigma_i^2 / n_i v_i \quad i = 1, 2.$$

cov = actual coverage probability (standard uncertainty = 0.0007)

wid = average half-width of interval

df = average calculated effective number of degrees of freedom

a_1	a_2	v_1	v_2	V_{ws} cov	wid	df	V_{ba} cov	wid	df	V_{hy} cov	wid	df
1	1	3	3	0.959	0.614	4.97	0.950	0.581	6.28	0.959	0.614	4.97
1	1	3	6	0.955	0.679	7.83	0.950	0.660	9.33	0.951	0.666	9.05
1	1	3	12	0.952	0.821	13.67	0.949	0.811	15.47	0.950	0.814	15.18
1	1	6	3	0.953	0.679	7.82	0.949	0.660	9.33	0.950	0.666	9.05
1	1	6	6	0.952	0.751	10.69	0.949	0.739	12.25	0.950	0.741	12.08
1	1	6	12	0.952	0.885	16.55	0.950	0.878	18.27	0.950	0.879	18.13
1	1	12	3	0.954	0.820	13.68	0.952	0.811	15.47	0.952	0.813	15.19
1	1	12	6	0.952	0.885	16.56	0.951	0.879	18.27	0.951	0.880	18.14
1	1	12	12	0.952	1.005	22.43	0.951	1.001	24.17	0.951	1.001	24.10
1	4	3	3	0.953	1.010	4.45	0.944	0.962	5.42	0.953	1.010	4.45
1	4	3	6	0.951	1.185	7.35	0.948	1.171	8.04	0.949	1.178	7.83
1	4	3	12	0.951	1.514	13.28	0.950	1.509	13.75	0.950	1.511	13.62
1	4	6	3	0.952	1.024	6.35	0.945	0.978	7.88	0.949	1.014	7.15
1	4	6	6	0.951	1.216	9.03	0.948	1.200	10.04	0.949	1.210	9.62
1	4	6	12	0.951	1.544	14.82	0.950	1.539	15.44	0.951	1.542	15.19
1	4	12	3	0.950	1.092	10.44	0.944	1.054	13.03	0.948	1.086	11.64
1	4	12	6	0.951	1.288	12.63	0.949	1.272	14.33	0.950	1.284	13.47
1	4	12	12	0.950	1.609	18.00	0.949	1.603	19.00	0.950	1.607	18.49
1	10	3	3	0.946	1.564	3.90	0.938	1.510	4.50	0.946	1.564	3.90
1	10	3	6	0.949	1.830	6.73	0.947	1.818	7.04	0.948	1.828	6.85
1	10	3	12	0.950	2.358	12.64	0.950	2.355	12.79	0.950	2.357	12.68
1	10	6	3	0.944	1.547	5.00	0.936	1.479	6.05	0.942	1.542	5.33
1	10	6	6	0.946	1.843	7.58	0.944	1.826	8.10	0.946	1.842	7.71
1	10	6	12	0.949	2.375	13.33	0.949	2.371	13.58	0.949	2.375	13.37
1	10	12	3	0.945	1.558	7.40	0.938	1.484	9.37	0.944	1.555	7.89
1	10	12	6	0.949	1.881	9.36	0.946	1.858	10.36	0.948	1.880	9.54
1	10	12	12	0.950	2.413	14.77	0.950	2.407	15.24	0.950	2.412	14.81
1	50	3	3	0.946	3.544	3.27	0.942	3.495	3.45	0.946	3.544	3.27
1	50	3	6	0.949	4.063	6.17	0.949	4.056	6.24	0.949	4.063	6.18
1	50	3	12	0.950	5.236	12.14	0.950	5.235	12.17	0.950	5.236	12.14
1	50	6	3	0.943	3.509	3.57	0.936	3.429	3.92	0.943	3.509	3.61
1	50	6	6	0.948	4.074	6.36	0.947	4.061	6.47	0.948	4.074	6.36
1	50	6	12	0.949	5.243	12.28	0.949	5.241	12.33	0.949	5.243	12.28
1	50	12	3	0.939	3.463	4.23	0.931	3.343	4.91	0.939	3.463	4.29
1	50	12	6	0.948	4.074	6.73	0.946	4.052	6.97	0.948	4.074	6.73
1	50	12	12	0.950	5.259	12.58	0.949	5.255	12.67	0.950	5.259	12.58

Table 3

Performances of 99% confidence intervals for $m = 2$ for 100,000 runs at various settings of the parameters $\sigma_1^2, \sigma_2^2, n_1$ and n_2 where

$$v_i = n_i - 1 \quad a_i = \sigma_i^2 / n_i v_i \quad i = 1, 2.$$

cov = actual coverage probability (standard uncertainty = 0.0007)

wid = average half-width of interval

df = average calculated effective number of degrees of freedom

a_1	a_2	v_1	v_2	V_{ws} cov	wid	df	V_{ba} cov	wid	df	V_{hy} cov	wid	df	V_{lt} cov	$k =$ wid	$\sqrt{0.5}$ df
1	1	3	3	0.993	0.977	4.97	0.989	0.888	6.29	0.993	0.977	4.97	0.981	0.752	9.93
1	1	3	6	0.992	0.997	7.82	0.990	0.951	9.33	0.990	0.967	9.05	0.989	0.925	10.22
1	1	3	12	0.990	1.141	13.66	0.989	1.119	15.46	0.990	1.126	15.18	0.990	1.122	14.99
1	1	6	3	0.992	0.997	7.82	0.990	0.951	9.34	0.990	0.967	9.05	0.988	0.924	10.23
1	1	6	6	0.992	1.064	10.68	0.990	1.038	12.25	0.991	1.043	12.07	0.990	1.035	12.11
1	1	6	12	0.990	1.218	16.55	0.990	1.204	18.26	0.990	1.206	18.13	0.990	1.208	17.47
1	1	12	3	0.991	1.142	13.67	0.990	1.120	15.46	0.990	1.127	15.18	0.990	1.123	14.99
1	1	12	6	0.990	1.218	16.55	0.990	1.204	18.26	0.990	1.206	18.13	0.990	1.208	17.47
1	1	12	12	0.990	1.365	22.44	0.990	1.356	24.18	0.990	1.357	24.11	0.990	1.361	23.13
1	4	3	3	0.990	1.674	4.45	0.986	1.544	5.42	0.990	1.674	4.45	0.975	1.152	10.60
1	4	3	6	0.990	1.746	7.35	0.989	1.711	8.03	0.989	1.728	7.82	0.987	1.630	9.21
1	4	3	12	0.990	2.105	13.29	0.990	2.096	13.76	0.990	2.099	13.63	0.990	2.094	13.73
1	4	6	3	0.990	1.588	6.35	0.987	1.468	7.89	0.988	1.563	7.16	0.983	1.248	12.05
1	4	6	6	0.990	1.757	9.04	0.989	1.720	10.05	0.989	1.744	9.64	0.988	1.653	11.37
1	4	6	12	0.990	2.140	14.81	0.989	2.129	15.43	0.990	2.135	15.18	0.989	2.123	15.66
1	4	12	3	0.989	1.586	10.42	0.988	1.494	13.00	0.988	1.572	11.61	0.987	1.391	16.41
1	4	12	6	0.989	1.814	12.64	0.988	1.776	14.34	0.989	1.804	13.48	0.988	1.730	15.79
1	4	12	12	0.990	2.208	18.01	0.989	2.195	19.01	0.989	2.204	18.49	0.989	2.185	19.59
1	10	3	3	0.987	2.696	3.90	0.983	2.540	4.50	0.987	2.696	3.90	0.966	1.674	10.95
1	10	3	6	0.989	2.733	6.73	0.988	2.704	7.04	0.989	2.727	6.85	0.986	2.527	8.62
1	10	3	12	0.990	3.292	12.64	0.990	3.286	12.80	0.990	3.291	12.69	0.989	3.278	12.97
1	10	6	3	0.986	2.551	5.00	0.981	2.363	6.05	0.984	2.540	5.34	0.973	1.730	12.44
1	10	6	6	0.988	2.718	7.57	0.987	2.677	8.10	0.988	2.715	7.70	0.984	2.506	10.08
1	10	6	12	0.990	3.311	13.32	0.990	3.302	13.57	0.990	3.310	13.36	0.990	3.286	14.00
1	10	12	3	0.986	2.414	7.39	0.982	2.223	9.36	0.985	2.407	7.89	0.978	1.826	16.04
1	10	12	6	0.988	2.723	9.34	0.986	2.668	10.33	0.987	2.720	9.51	0.984	2.520	12.90
1	10	12	12	0.990	3.349	14.77	0.989	3.336	15.23	0.990	3.348	14.80	0.989	3.311	16.09
1	50	3	3	0.986	6.403	3.27	0.983	6.253	3.44	0.986	6.403	3.27	0.954	3.600	10.63
1	50	3	6	0.990	6.139	6.17	0.989	6.121	6.23	0.990	6.138	6.18	0.986	5.696	7.68
1	50	3	12	0.990	7.333	12.14	0.990	7.331	12.17	0.990	7.333	12.14	0.990	7.323	12.25
1	50	6	3	0.982	6.210	3.58	0.978	5.970	3.92	0.982	6.209	3.62	0.954	3.600	11.38
1	50	6	6	0.989	6.116	6.36	0.988	6.084	6.48	0.989	6.116	6.36	0.984	5.642	8.16
1	50	6	12	0.990	7.332	12.28	0.990	7.328	12.33	0.990	7.332	12.28	0.989	7.313	12.50
1	50	12	3	0.981	5.948	4.23	0.976	5.602	4.92	0.980	5.948	4.28	0.958	3.626	12.97
1	50	12	6	0.989	6.103	6.72	0.988	6.047	6.96	0.989	6.103	6.72	0.984	5.595	9.01
1	50	12	12	0.989	7.351	12.58	0.989	7.342	12.67	0.989	7.351	12.58	0.989	7.315	12.99

12,12	1	2	4	4	4	2	1
6,12	0	2	3	8	12		
3,12	0	1	3	12			
6,6				16			
3,6	2			28			
3,3				54			
	1/50	1/10	1/4	1/1	4/1	10/1	50/1

Figure 1: Comparison of the performances of v_{ba} and v_{ws} using the data of Table 2. The x-axis labels are a_i/a_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$. The y-axis labels are v_i, v_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$, where in each case $v_i \leq v_j$. The table entries are the proportional reduction in average width of the confidence interval using v_{ba} in place of v_{ws} , in tenths of percent. For example, the average width of the confidence interval using v_{ba} with $a_1 = 1, a_2 = 4, v_1 = 12$ and $v_2 = 6$ was 1.2% shorter than with v_{ws} . Entries are given for the parameter settings where v_{ba} is deemed to perform at least as well as v_{ws} .

12,12	0	0	1	4	1	0	0
6,12	0	0	1	7	3		0
3,12	0	0	2	9			0
6,6	0	1	5	13	5	1	0
3,6	0		6	19	10		0
3,3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	1/50	1/10	1/4	1/1	4/1	10/1	50/1

Figure 2: Comparison of the performances of v_{hy} and v_{ws} using the data of Table 2. The x-axis labels are a_i/a_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$. The y-axis labels are v_i, v_j for $i = 1, j = 2$ and $i = 2, j = 1$, where in each case $v_i \leq v_j$. The table entries are the proportional reduction in average width of the confidence interval using v_{hy} in place of v_{ws} , in tenths of percent. For example, the average width of the confidence interval using v_{hy} with $a_1 = 1, a_2 = 4, v_1 = 12$ and $v_2 = 6$ was 0.3% shorter than with v_{ws} . Entries are given for the parameter settings where v_{hy} is deemed to perform at least as well as v_{ws} .

An implication of the tables and figures is that the hybrid estimate v_{hy} performs better than v_{ws} if a_1 and a_2 are similar with interval widths being reduced by about 1%, and has almost the same level of performance as v_{ws} in other cases. Similar results were observed for 1000 simulations with $m = 3$ in a table not presented here. Further work would be to investigate results for $m = 3$ with more than 1000 simulations to increase precision, and investigate alternative coefficients in the definition of v_{hy} than the fixed choice of 0.25.

As mentioned a third performance criterion for confidence intervals constructed repeatedly under the same situations could be the variability in the width of the confidence interval. The variance of the half-widths of each confidence interval for 10,000 simulations with parameters setting the same as first, second and last rows of Table 3 respectively are tabulated below.

	$a_2 = 1, v_1 = v_2 = 3$	$a_2 = 1, v_1 = 3, v_2 = 6$	$a_2 = 50, v_1 = v_2 = 12$
v_{ws}	3.42	2.63	114.1
v_{ba}	3.10	2.49	114.3
v_{ba}^*	3.69	2.77	114.0
v_{hy}	3.42	2.58	114.1
$v_{it}(k = \sqrt{0.5})$	2.41	2.37	114.5
v_{fi}			113.3

The first two columns of data suggest there are considerable differences in the variability of the widths for low degrees of freedom, and these differences tend to favour the alternative estimates v_{ba} and v_{hy} over v_{ws} . These results for this third criterion therefore lend support to the possible use of an alternative to v_{ws} .

9.2 Concluding summary of results

Tables 1-3 suggest that the Welch-Satterthwaite formula (2) performs surprisingly well in terms of actual coverage probability. The main alternatives investigated lead to estimates of effective degrees of freedom which are higher, so that the confidence intervals are shorter. These alternatives may then be useful in cases where the Welch-Satterthwaite formula gives a conservative interval, i.e., an interval with actual coverage probability greater than the nominal value. These cases represent only a subset of the points in the space formed by the unknown parameters. Indeed the Welch-Satterthwaite formula only appears conservative when the unknown values of $\sigma_i^2/n_i v_i$ are similar. The simulations suggest that the hybrid method of v_{hy} , which uses the bias adjusted estimate v_{ba} when the data are favourable, is an alternative to v_{ws} over the whole parameter space for $m = 2$ and $m = 3$. It gives a small improvement in the confidence interval where the values of $\sigma_i^2/n_i v_i$ are similar, and very little change in other cases. However as simplicity is also an important criterion for the usefulness of a technique it is debatable if this improvement in performance outweighs the cost of using a more complex method.

Lastly, we make the point that the hybrid approach might instead use $v_{ba,welch}$ of (14), which performed almost identically to v_{ba} in trials with $m = 2$, and which Welch compared favourably with his exact solution[5] (for general m). By contrast v_{ba} was derived by dropping the third and fourth terms correction terms of the approximate equation (11) with no theoretical justification. In the absence of simulation results with $m > 3$ for v_{ba} , $v_{ba,welch}$ might be preferred.

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